

Yethapur Sri Muthumalai Murugan Temple

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Abstract: The worship of Lord of Muruga has got a prominent place in Tamil Nadu. There are many temples for Lord Muruga who is considered as the Tamil deity. The important one among them is Sri Muthumalai Murugan temple which is located at a place called Yethapur at Pethanayakanpalayam taluk in Salem district. A businessman named Mr. Natarajan and his younger son Mr. N. Sridhar who belong to Athur in Salem district, decided to build a huge statue of Lord Muruga as it was in their place Malaysia which is popularly known as Pathumalai Murugan by giving their 2 acres of land. As Mr. Natarajan has passed away at this situation, his younger son Mr. N. Sridhar has continued this work. The construction of this temple took six years and the consecration ceremony of this temple took place after 10 a.m. on 6th April in the year 2022. The statue of Lord Muruga which is 146 feet long astonishes everyone who visit this temple. The statue of Sri Muthumalai Murugan which faces southwards is painted using five colours and looks brave along with the altar of the main deity. Various rituals and festivals have been celebrated in a grand manner in this temple. Thousands of devotees from the places around this temple would visit here during these festival times. A person named Mr. N. Sridhar who is the founder and chairman of Sri Muthumalai Murugan Trust is administering this temple. Sri Muthumalai Murugan temple is the pilgrim center and tourist place adorned by the devotees.

Keywords: Sri Muthumalai Murugan, Sri Muthumalai Murugan Trust, Surasamharam, The world's tallest Lord Muruga statue, Yethapur.

Introduction

Hinduism is older than any other religion in the world and it consists of six divisions namely Shaivism, Vaishnavism, Kanapathyam, Kaumaram, Saktham and Sauram. Among these, Kaurmaram is the religion which worships Lord Muruga as the main deity. Kumaran who is worshipped as Lord Muruga in Tamil Nadu has the peacock as His vehicle and rooster as His flag. Lord Muruga is considered to be the Tamil deity. The Sangam literature denotes Lord Muruga as Seyon. It is believed that wherever there is a hill, Kumaran will be there. The temples of Lord Muruga have been built in all the places where Tamil people live. As per the principle formatted by the ancient scholars that not to live in the place where there is no temple, many temples are there for Lord Muruga all around Tamil Nadu. The places which are apt for Lord Muruga are called six abodes of Lord Muruga namely Thiruparankundaram, Thiruchiralaivai (Tiruchendur), Thiruvavinankudi (Pazhani), Thiruveragam (Swamimalai), Kundruthoradal (Tiruthani) and Pazhamuthircholai respectively. Apart from these, there are many other temples for Lord Muruga in Tamil Nadu. Yethapur Sri Muthumalai Murugan temple which has the world's tallest statue of Lord Muruga is significant one among them.

Location

Sri Muthumalai Murugan temple is located adjacent to the Salem – Chennai National Highway at the outer area of a place called Yethapur which is near Vazhapadi at Pethanayakkanpalayam taluk in Salem district. This temple is situated 42 Kilometers away

from Salem, 14.5 Kilometers away from Athur, 3 Kilometers away from Pethanayakkanpalayam and 305.5 kilometers away from Chennai.

Temple History

The businessman named Mr. Natarajan and his younger son named Mr. N. Sridhar who are the devotees of Lord Muruga from Athur in Salem district bought 50 acres of land near Yethapur Bus stop in 2015 and decided to build a statue of Lord Muruga as the most popular Pathumalai Murugan which was there in the Malaysian capital Kuala Lumpur in 2 acres of land. So it has been decided by calling Mr. R. Thiyagarajan who has sculpted the statue of Lord Muruga in Malaysia and build the tallest statue of Lord Muruga like Lord Muruga in Malaysia. On this basis, the construction work of building the 146 feet statue of Lord Muruga started and the rituals for earth were done on 6th of September 2016 by bringing soil from the six abodes. At this stage, as Mr. Natarajan died due to illness in the year 2018, his younger son Mr. N. Sridhar continued this work. The construction work of this temple happened for six years. It has to be denoted that this statue of Lord Muruga has been built in a way in which it gives dharshan for five lakhs people at a time.

After the completion of the construction work of this temple, the consecration of this temple was held by pouring holy water on the kalasa along with chanting of Harohara by the devotees on 6th April 2022 after 10 a.m. The lamp worship has been shown to the 146 feet Lord Muruga and the Moolavar. Flowers of different colours have thrown for the 146 feet statue of Lord Muruga. The devotees from various districts such as Salem, Perambalur, Kallakurichi and Namakal participated and worshipped in this ceremony.

Structure, Architecture and Sculpture

This temple is situated 329 meters above the sea level. Sri Muthumalai Murugan statue which faces south along with the main deity looks bravely in the two acres of land. This temple consists of many portions such as sanctum sactorum, Artha Mandapa, Maha Mandapa, Yagasalai Mandapa, Vimana, altar, flag post, peacock, holy presence of Lord Vinayaga, 146 feet statue of Lord Muruga, lift, Madapalli and office respectively. Now the construction work of building a 60 feet height of huge tower with five levels started from 24.11.2023 and is going on. The main deity of this temple is Sri Muthumalai Murugan. The sanctum sanctorum of this temple which is heptagon in shape faces towards eastern direction. They have sculpted the stucco sculptures of the images of Lord Muruga as in six abodes in the outer walls around the sanctum sanctorum. In the same way, they have sculpted the images of Lord Muruga in the Vimana too as stucco sculptures. The idol taken out in procession who is Subramaniyar shows out with Valli and Deivanai in the Maha Mandapa of the temple. There are stucco sculptures of Lord Shiva and Parvati in a sitting posture, Lord Vinayaga sitting on the right side of Lord Shiva and Lord Muruga sitting on the lap of Parvati as a small boy are shown in the northern wall of Yagasalai Mandapa. The 146 feet statue of Sri Muthumalai Murugan which is situated above the Maha Mandapa of this temple astonishes everyone. When compared on the worldwide the statue of Sri Muthumalai Murugan which is situated in Yethapur is the tallest among the other ones. The height of the statue is 114 feet long. The height of the pedestal is 32 feet long. So totally it has the height of 146 feet.

The holy body of Lord Muruga which is sculpted realistically is sculpted in a way in which Lord Muruga comes in reality with a smiling face and appears before us. This statue of Lord Muruga appears with the right hand which is in Abayahasta pose which means the protection affording hand pose, holding a spear in his left hand and wearing a gem studded crown and wearing beautiful jewels and clothes in a standing posture and blesses the

devotees. The statue of Sri Muthumalai Murugan is painted with five colours and looks radiantly. The model statue of this big statue is situated there near the big statue in a small level. A lift has also been made near the tallest statue. Through this lift, the devotees climb up to the top and do Abhisheka to the spear made of five metals which is inside the spear in the hand of Lord Muruga. After that when they see the mountain which is situated opposite to this statue, it looks as if Sri Muthumalai Murugan lies down and views the sky.

The Specialty of the Temple

The very special thing in this temple is the world's tallest statue of Lord Muruga. Another specialty is the golden car procession which takes place on waxing moon Sashti and other important special days at 7 p.m. in the evening. It has to be denoted that the parking fees is not collected for parking the vehicles in this temple.

Worship and Festivals

This temple opens from 6.30 a.m. in the morning till 9 p.m. in the evening. The ritual takes place as per Kumarathandira tradition three times a day. The devotees visit this temple high in number on Tuesdays, Fridays and Sundays and the fasting days like Kiruthigai, Sashti, Full Moon and New Moon days and festival days. During the time of the festivals, the main deity appears in gold Armor. Many festivals like Tamil New Year in the month of Chithirai, Vaikasi Visagam in the month of Vaikasi, Aadikiruthigai and Aadiperukku in the month of Aadi, Vinayagar Chaturthi in the month of Avani, Kandha Sashti in the month of Aippasi, Karthigai Deepam festival in Karthigai month, English New Year in Margazhi month, Thaiposam in Thai month and Panguni Uthiram festival in the month of Panguni have been celebrated in a special manner in this temple.

The special days of this temple every month are Sashti and Karthigai days. A grand decoration and special ritual are done for the main deity for the Aadiperukku festival in this temple. Vinayagar Chaturthi is celebrated in a grand manner for Sri Sankara Vinayaga in this temple during the month of Avani. Sathru Samhara ritual and *Yaga* are held for six days starting from waxing moon day prathamai of Aippasi month till Sashti Thithi. The special ritual and *Yaga* are done for the main deity on these six days. The six day which is called Surasamharam is celebrated grandly. The preaching of *Kantha Purana* and music programs are held during the night on these six days. Many people from in and around the temple take part on this occasion. The Thanurmatha ritual takes place at 5 a.m. in the morning during the month of Margazhi. The Panguni Uthiram festival is celebrated as three days festival in a grand manner. Hundreds of devotees carry milk pot and perform Abhisheka for the main deity on the day of Panguni Uthiram.

The preparations for the festivals of this temple are undertaken by Mr. N. Sridhar who is the founder and chairman of Sri Muthumalai Murugan Trust. The food offering is done from 12.30 p.m. to 2 p.m. in the evening everyday in this temple. The food offering for the needy is given to thousands of people during the festival times.

Consecrations

The people who worship Lord Muruga pray for their needs and pray that they will take obligation that they will carry Kavadi, Anga Pradhatchana, piercing the spear, offering hair and rooster as their offering to the God if their obligations get fulfilled. Then they do Abhisheka for the God and give offerings to the temple. Apart from these, many people offer food to the poor and the needy.

Temple Administration

A person named Mr. N. Sridhar who is the founder and chairman of Sri Muthumalai Murugan Trust has been administering this temple.

Conclusion

Yethapur Murugan temple has been the adorable pilgrimage center and tourist spot praised by the devotees. The devotees call this Lord Muruga as the one and only deity and call Him Kaliyugavarathan and worship Him vigourously. Lord Muruga also gives blessings satisfied by their worship. Many devotees not only from Tamil Nadu but also from other states such as Karnataka, Kerala and Andhra Pradesh visit this temple. So it is not an exaggeration to say that this temple has been one among the important pilgrim centers in Tamil Nadu.

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